

Multidisciplinary Workshops for Early Career Researchers in Arctic Social Sciences and Engineering, Mid-term report, May 2023

The project "*Multidisciplinary Workshops for Early Career Researchers in Arctic Social Sciences and Engineering*," funded by UArctic, was initiated with the primary objective of conducting a series of workshops where Early Career Researchers (ECRs) in Arctic Social Sciences and Engineering could present their research to local Arctic communities. The goal of the project is to engage in discussions on the impacts of climate change and permafrost thaw on these communities, how to manage risk and adaptation locally, and how to focus future research initiatives.

Three workshops were organized in high-Arctic communities in Svalbard, Greenland, and Canada. The workshops served as a platform for the ECRs to disseminate their research results to the communities and provided a space for discussing the relevance and applicability of the research and results. Community representatives were invited to reflect with ECRs on adaptation and mitigation strategies. Each workshop also featured a session specifically focused on the perception of risks related to permafrost thaw impacts on the community, and discussions of community needs and interests, to help the ECRs shape their future research direction based on co-design principles and active community participation.

Workshops were conducted in Ilulissat, Greenland (January 2023), Inuvik region, Canada (February 2023), and Longyearbyen, Svalbard (March 2023). These workshops brought together early-career researchers (ECRs), senior scientists, stakeholders and local and indigenous people to discuss the impacts of permafrost thaw, risk perceptions, adaptation strategies, and the potential use of indicators. A separate report from each workshop is attached to this project report, and brief summaries are included below.

Ilulissat, Greenland (January 2023)

The Ilulissat workshop involved a series of meetings with stakeholders. Discussions with Avannaata Municipality focused on the municipality's perceptions of risk and strategies to adapt, and the definition of new indicators of permafrost thaw impacts. Meetings were also held with the public housing administration company, INI, and the public utilities company, Nukissiorfiit, to discuss their challenges related to permafrost thaw. An open community workshop was held with presentations of research activities and findings relevant to the community by ECRs and senior researchers, and we tested a concept for active participation in quantifying the local perception of risk from permafrost thaw.

Inuvik region, Canada (February 2023)

The Inuvik region workshop, known as the "Permafrost Days 2023," involved interactions with about 40 locals with different professional and ethnic backgrounds. The workshop activities resulted in useful insights on risk perceptions, adaptation strategies, and the possible use of indicators. The group learned about the close relationship between Inuit and First Nation societies and their ancestral lands, and how infrastructure challenges related to permafrost thaw and climate change are widespread and diverse across the region. Workshops were held in both Inuvik and Aklavik and brought together both local and foreign researchers with the indigenous and local population in active discussions.

Longyearbyen, Svalbard (March 2023)

The Longyearbyen workshop was a two-day event that brought together early career and senior researchers from the natural sciences, engineering, and social sciences. The workshop aimed to present and discuss ongoing permafrost research methods, activities, and results in Longyearbyen. Societal impacts of permafrost thaw and related adaptation measures, identified knowledge needs and research priorities, and collaborations between science and society were discussed. The event included a session with local stakeholders invited from public administration and the private sector to discuss permafrost impacts on infrastructure in Longyearbyen and the possibilities for adaptation actions. In a session with participation of local and visiting researchers, current research priorities, gaps and needs were discussed, and Indicators and variables to quantify the impacts of permafrost thaw were identified. Finally, an open community workshop was held with 14 short scientific presentations, and the participation of 88 local visitors.

General outcome

The workshops were successful in maintaining a balance of gender representation among the participants. The workshops also provided opportunities for both early career and senior researchers to engage with local and regional organizations, stakeholders, and community members. In total, the project has so far brought together 21 ECRs and 18 senior researchers in 3 Arctic communities, and ensured a platform through which the research community has interacted with more than 200 indigenous and local individuals.

In all three workshops, the importance of interdisciplinary research to understand the complex and interconnected issues surrounding permafrost and its impacts was highlighted. The workshops were successful in fostering interesting discussions, knowledge exchange, and planning of future joint activities. They reinforced existing and created many new connections, providing ample opportunities for both formal and informal exchange between the different stakeholders. The workshop activities also highlighted significant differences in natural conditions, as well as cultural and regulatory structures across the three regions, that impact the consequences of permafrost thaw and perception of related risks in the different communities.

As a follow-up on the workshop activities, the project team is now working on processing the collected data in preparation for a publication on consequences of permafrost thaw and the local perception of risk in these communities.

Thomas Ingeman-Nielsen
Associate Professor
2023-05-31

Attached:

Report on Ilulissat Workshop, January 2023
Report on Inuvik region Workshop, February 2023
Report on Longyearbyen Workshop, March 2023

Interdisciplinary Permafrost Workshop

Ilulissat, Greenland, January 2023

Summarizing statement

The Ilulissat workshop was conducted in the week of January 9 to January 16, 2023.

It consisted of a series of meetings with relevant stakeholders, and culminated with an open community workshop in the cultural center in Ilulissat (see attached the invitation and the program). ECR Ulla Timlin had a presentation and ECR Leneisja Jungsberg was only on-line, since attendance, unfortunately, was limited by last minute cancellations due to illness.

A meeting was conducted with the Technical department of Avannaata Kommunia on 2023-01-10. Five representatives of the municipal technical department participated. ECR Ulla Timlin was present and presented results on a health survey and qualitative interviews conducted in the region. Another ECR Johanna Scheer joined the meeting online to present results of work to develop a road network hazard mapping algorithm. Three senior scientists, Arja Rautio, Joan Nymand Larsen, and Thomas Ingeman-Nielsen participated in the meeting. During the meeting, we also discussed the municipality's perceptions of risk and strategies to adapt, and we discussed the definition of new indicators of permafrost thaw impacts.

A meeting with two employees of the public housing administration company, INI, was conducted on 2023-01-11. ECR Ulla Timlin and 3 senior scientists participated in person. We discussed the adverse challenges in housing administration and their relation to permafrost thaw, and how issues differ based on geographical region. INI helped us validate our mapping of risk perception, and provided input on potential definition and use of indicators.

Nukissiorfiit, the public utilities company, met with us on 2023-01-12. Approximately 10 employees of Nukissiorfiit participated, along with ECR Ulla Timlin and the 3 senior scientists. We discussed current challenges for supply infrastructure on permafrost, especially powerlines, sewers, and district heating. Nukissiorfiit helped us to validate the risk perceptions mapping, and provided input on potential definition and use of indicators of PF thaw.

On 2023-01-12 the ECRs together with the senior scientists also met with Munck, the airport construction company, and several additional smaller meetings were held with other stakeholders over the course of the week.

On 2023-01-14 we had an open community meeting in the culture center. Here the work of the 3 ECRs was presented to the general public, and presentations were also made by Joan Nymand Larsen and Thomas Ingeman-Nielsen. Following the presentations, we had an activity to let community members indicate the hazard factors of permafrost that are of importance to them and rate the impacts of these hazards on different perception domains. We also discussed the definition of indicators of PF thaw impacts, and possible adaptation

strategies. A total of 17 community members participated in the workshop. Of these, 10 were female (58%) and 7 were male (42%).

In total, during the workshop week of January 9-16, we interacted with close to 40 locals with different professional and ethnic backgrounds. The workshop activities resulted in useful insights on risk perceptions, adaptation strategies, and the possible use of indicators. The ECRs in particular gained valuable experience in conducting these workshops, that will be useful in the planning of the upcoming activities in Inuvik and Longyearbyen. Overall, the gender balance was approximately 33 % female and 67 % male.

Organizers:

Johanna Scheer (ECR)
Leneisja Jungsberg (ECR)

Researchers involved:

Ulla Timlin (ECR)
Leneisja Jungsberg (ECR, online)
Johanna Scheer (ECR, online)
Joan Nyman Larsen,
Thomas Ingeman-Nielsen,
Arja Rautio,

Ilulissat KPIs	Count	Gender balance
ECRs	3	100% female
Senior researchers	3	75% female, 25% male
Open community meeting attendees	17	58% female, 42% male
Meetings with technical stakeholders	approx. 23	approx. 13% female, 87% male

Interdisciplinary Permafrost Workshop

Inuvik region, Canada, February 2023

Summarizing statement

The “Permafrost Days 2023” (UARctic transdisciplinary workshops) were a series of events organized by Susanna Gartler between the 7th to 9th of February in Inuvik and Aklavik. They brought together scientists with local stakeholders, strengthened networks and provided opportunities to discuss the relevance and applicability of scientific results with the communities of Inuvik, Aklavik and Tuktoyaktuk. The initiative was very well received and included three full days of discussions, workshops and scientific presentations. In addition to the invited scientists, three representatives of the Inuvialuit Aklavik and Tuktoyaktuk Hunters and Trappers Committees (AHTC & THTC), as well as one of the co-organizers of the Canadian Permafrost Association 2022 conference were officially invited and attended all activities. A website was created with the full program: permafrost2023.wordpress.com. CBC, the Canadian Broadcasting Corporation, was present during all three days, the outcome of which one can find here: "[Sinking In](#)". The “Permafrost Days 2023” were attended by representatives of a large number of local organizations and governments, and created an excellent opportunity for effective co-creation of knowledge, science communication & outreach. The events reinforced existing and created many new connections and provided ample opportunities for both formal and informal exchange between the different stakeholders.

Program

The Tuesday workshop, which took place in the Permafrost Room of the Mackenzie Hotel in Inuvik on the 7th of February, was attended by a total of more than twenty professionals, of which six were female. The attendees were affiliated with a large variety of local and regional organizations. These included the AHTC, the THTC, the Gwich'in Tribal Council (Department of Lands and Resources), the Gwich'in Development Corporation, the Aurora Research Institute, the NWT Department of Infrastructure and the Department of Natural Resources, the Hamlet of Inuvik, the Inuvik Greenhouse, the NWT Geological Survey, the Inuvialuit Regional Corporation and Parks Canada. Key hazards, socio-economic and health-related consequences, and indicators of permafrost thaw impacts were discussed, as well as adaptation measures. Nine local and international ECRs participated in the event. In addition, we had two online participants, one being a local news reporter.

On Wednesday the 8th a public conference day took place at the Midnight Sun Complex in Inuvik. More than twenty participants attended the fourteen scientific public presentations and the roundtable discussion in the evening (see the full program here: "[Permafrost Days 2023](#)") in addition to the fifteen scientists who took part, of which eight were ECRs. We also had six online participants. The gender ratio was approximately half/half. On Thursday we held a workshop in Aklavik, similar to the one held on Tuesday in Inuvik but with a different audience and two presentations of research results from Aklavik by ECRs. We had twelve

participants in the beginning who were mainly members of the Aklavik Hunters and Trappers Committee, of which three were female. Ten more people joined later, including the mayor of the Hamlet of Aklavik, one of our local research assistants and a female Indigenous Elder. Overall, we had twenty-two local participants, who were mostly Inuvialuit and Gwich'in First Nation members, as well as nine of which four were ECRs.

Take-aways for early-career and senior researchers

Overall, the group learned about the close relationship between Inuit and First Nation societies and their ancestral lands, and how infrastructure (especially transport infrastructure) in this particular cultural context includes elements such as rivers, ocean ice, trails, and the tundra. Individuals and families are considered more responsible for adapting to changes than for example compared to Greenland where municipalities and institutions are seen as having more responsibility for climate change adaptation. The importance of subsistence practices and the associated challenges posed by climate change were discussed. It was noted that more representation from women, including youth and elders, would have been beneficial. The participants also gained insight into the health benefits of relying on country food. The group discussed the need for collaboration between traditional practices and new technology to adapt to the impacts of climate change. They identified challenges such as lack of local policies and training, as well as urgent and complex issues like pollution and flooding. Participants suggested a focus on concrete adaptation and mitigation measures, and the importance of working with local Indigenous communities.

The question of building codes for different latitudes was also discussed, as well as the importance of dialogue and exchange rather than dictating solutions, and that workshops such as the “Permafrost Days” provided good opportunities for discussions around permafrost and innovative adaptation practices. Participants noted that regional issues must be solved in regional ways, while they also learned about the Canadian state and the Indigenous governance structures in the region. The group acknowledged the difficult history of colonialism and residential schools in the area, but expressed hope for moving forward and healing. Some local Indigenous attendees said they would push for more science to inform adaptation efforts in the future, which was seen as a very good result, but it was also emphasized that scientists should be prepared for the specific cultural and political context of the region.

Take-away from PI Beaufort Sea Delta part of Nunataryuk

The UArctic workshop provided an opportunity to verify the risk assessment conducted within the Nunataryuk project with different audiences and turned out to be a highly effective science communication and outreach event. It provided ample opportunities for dialogue between science (with both local scientists and researchers from other regions that experience similar problems), local/regional communities and Indigenous governments. Challenges faced by northern communities due to permafrost thaw were discussed in great depth. The lack of sustainable solutions for energy supply and the need for constant maintenance of infrastructure were highlighted. Exposure to contaminants and diseases from

permafrost thaw, decrease in water quality, and infrastructure failures were identified as major concerns. Amongst the topics that were discussed were longer thawing seasons and milder winters, the balance between Indigenous and Western lifestyles, innovative construction solutions, and the role of researchers, journalists, and policy-makers. The Aklavik Hunters and Trappers Committee expressed a higher concern for risks related to permafrost thaw overall in comparison to the mixed group of professionals in Inuvik, including concerns about decreased water quality, uncertainties in regards to exposure to contaminants and infectious diseases, the disruption of travel routes, general mobility and supplies, and infrastructure failures. Adaptation to changing conditions using Indigenous knowledge and innovations such as new building materials and architectural forms were also discussed. Overall, the UArctic workshop(s) were a great success and have helped consolidate and create many new connections that will be extremely useful going forward in the future.

Organizer:

Susanna Gartler (ECR)

Researchers involved:

Susanna Gartler (ECR)

Elizabeth Hardy-Lachance (ECR)

Johanna Scheer (ERC)

Sona Tomašková (ECR)

Ulla Timlin (ECR)

Alice Wilson (ECR)

Jennifer Humphries (ECR)

Erika Hille (ECR)

Celtie Ferguson (ECR)

Jean-Pascal Bilodeau

Jón Haukur Ingimundarson

Thomas Ingeman-Nielsen

Joan Nymand Larsen

Pier Paul Overduin

Arja Rautio

Specially invited local participants

William Storr (AHTC President)

Dorothy Erigaktoak (AHTC Director)

Ikalualuq (THTC Director)

Stephan Walke (FN NND, CPA Conference 2022 Co-Organizer)

Inuvik region KPIs	Count	Gender balance
ECRs	9	100% female
Senior researchers	6	33% female, 67% male
Meeting with professionals from local and regional organizations	20	30% female, 70% male
Meetings with HTCs & other stakeholders	22	50% female, 50% male
Open community meeting attendees	>26	approx. 50% female, 50% male

Interdisciplinary Permafrost Workshop

Longyearbyen, Svalbard, March 2023

Summarizing statement

Permafrost is underlying large parts of the Arctic landscapes, and is an important part of the Arctic Earth system. It is rapidly changing due to climate change. To explore and understand the changes and their impacts on local societies, a two-day workshop "Longyearbyen permafrost activities" was held at The University Centre in Svalbard (UNIS) on 15-16 March. The workshop brought together early career and senior researchers from the natural sciences, engineering and social sciences researching permafrost in various projects in Longyearbyen, Russia, and Greenland. UArctic network funding enabled this as the last in a row of three community-based permafrost workshops, the first two held in Ilulissat, Greenland and Aklavik and Inuvik, Canada earlier this spring.

The aim of the workshop was to present and discuss ongoing permafrost research methods, activities and results in Longyearbyen, focusing on research conducted by early career researchers. Societal impacts of permafrost thaw and adaptation measures, identified knowledge needs and research priorities, and collaborations between science and society were discussed. The PermaMeteoCommunity, Nunataryuk, PermaRich and PCCH-Arctic projects were presented together with the Shared Arctic Variable Permafrost of the Arctic Passion project. The projects are EU funded, funded by the Norwegian Research Council, UNIS and the FRAM Centre.

Sharing project results with local stakeholders and the general public was a main focus. Representatives from the Local Council and the Governor of Svalbard joined us for a session presenting projects and research findings, and discussing adaptation, science and society, and permafrost knowledge needs. In a public evening outreach seminar 14 researchers presented glimpses of their research followed by an open meeting between the researchers and the public to further discuss permafrost in Longyearbyen while enjoying coffee and cake in the UNIS cafeteria. The seminar was attended by 88 local participants.

The workshop was a great success, with interesting discussions, knowledge exchange learning about each other's research and planning of future joint activities. We are grateful for the collaboration between the projects, to UNIS for hosting the workshop, and to UArctic for funding this event. The workshop highlighted the importance of interdisciplinary research to understand the complex and interconnected issues surrounding permafrost and its impacts. We look forward to continuing the dialogue!

Organizer:

Alexandra Meyer (ECR)

Researchers involved:

Susanna Gartler (ECR)

Leneisja Jungsberg (ECR)

Alexandra Meyer (ECR)

Olga Povoroznyuk (ECR)

Ulla Timlin (ECR)

Ilkka Matero (ECR)

Sarah Strand (ECR)

Knut Tveit (ECR)

Mederick (ECR)

Hanne H. Christiansen

Elisabeth Angell

Andy Hodson

Arne Instanes

Heikki Lihavainen

Aleksey Shestov

Anatoly Sinitsyn

Peter Schweitzer

Thomas Ingeman-Nielsen

Longyearbyen KPIs	Count	Gender balance
ECRs	9	67% female, 33% male
Senior researchers	9	22% female, 78% male
Open community meeting attendees	88	68% female, 32% male
Meetings with technical stakeholders	9	66% female, 34% male